

Application of Association Theory for the Interpretation of Non-idealities in the Enthalpies and Internal Pressures of some Binary Liquid Mixtures

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The concepts of association theory was applied to liquid mixtures and the values of a characteristic parameter (B^E) were calculated for some typical binaries. Further, the importance of B^E was discussed to interpret the non-idealities and apparent inconsistencies in enthalpies, internal pressures as well as heats of evaporation of the binaries considered. It was concluded that B^E is a better indicator for the assessment of the resultant variations in the nature and the extent of molecular structurations leading to non-idealities in liquid mixtures.

Non-idealities in mixture properties are the consequences of variations in the nature and the extent of interactions among the molecular species present in liquid mixtures. According to association theory, liquids consist of associated multimers in equilibrium with unassociated unimers whose concentration is small and existence transitory. Such multimers are formed due to aggregation of unimers as a result of molecular interaction or so-called association bond formation and may be termed as complex or simple depending on the state and the nature of aggregation involved. The situation is represented by the equation,

where α is the average number of unimers in multimers while C_1 , C_{α} and $C_{\alpha+1}$ represent the concentrations of the unimers, α -mers and $(\alpha+1)$ -mers respectively. In a liquid at a given temperature and pressure, α is generally greater than 5 and has a small range of variation. Complex multimers usually consist of multiply bonded unimers which are close-packed in such a way that their removal is not possible by a single or a series sequential single bond-breaks. Only a multi-bond break is capable of removing a multiply bonded unimer from the parent complex multimer. On the other hand, the simple or less complex multimers usually consist of simply bonded unimers which are loosely packed in such a way that any unimer held in one of these multimers could always be removed by a single or a series of sequential single bond-breaks.

Accordingly, in the case of complex multimers formed by multiply-bonded unimers, the single breaks or sequential breaks of intraparticle association bonds do not lead to any increase in the number of molecular species in the system. While in the case of simple or less complex multimers formed by simply bonded unimers, the single or sequential single breaks of intra-particle association bonds

always lead to an increase in the number of molecular species in the system.

In view of the differing consequences of such multi-bond breaks as well as single or a series of sequential single-bond breaks within multimers as assumed in association theory, it appears worthwhile to interpret the nonidealities in enthalpies and internal pressures together with some other related properties of a few typical binary liquid mixtures in terms of a characteristic parameter depending on such consequences of the association theory. The present paper is an attempt in this direction.

Theoretical : Following the a ssoication theory approach, the enthalpy change (ΔH) in the temperature range 0 to T K for any system, when the external pressure (P_0) is constant, is given by the equation¹,

$$\Delta H = H - H_0 = 2.5 BRT - \int_0^T (P_0 + P_i) d(V - V_s) \quad (2)$$

where P_i is the internal pressure, V the molar volume and $(V - V_s)$ the molar free volume with V_s taken as solid like volume, R the gas constant and T the temperature while B is a characteristic parameter of the association theory and is given by the equation²,

$$B = \frac{b P_i V_s}{R \gamma_s} \quad (3)$$

with

$$\gamma_s = a - bT \quad (4)$$

where γ_s is the surface tension and a and b are constants. Since the free volume $(V - V_s)$ may safely be taken as equal to zero at 0 K, P_0 remains constant and P_i varies slowly with $(V - V_s)$, and we can write

$$\int_0^T (P_0 + P_i) d(V - V_s) \simeq (P_0 + P_i)(V - V_s) \quad (5)$$

Incorporating equation (5) in equation (2), we get

$$\Delta H = 2.5 BRT - (P_e + P_i)V - V_e \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) as applied to mixtures takes the following form,

$$\Delta H_m = 2.5 B_m RT - (P_e + P_{im})(V_m - V_{im}) \quad (7)$$

where the subscript m stands for the mixtures and ΔH_m and B_m are given by

$$\Delta H_m = (\sum_i X_i H_i) + \Delta H_m^M \quad (8)$$

$$B_m = (\sum_i X_i B_i) + B^E \quad (9)$$

where ΔH^M is the enthalpy of mixing which is same as the excess enthalpy (ΔH^E), B^E the excess in the association theory characteristic parameter (B), X the mole fraction and the subscript i stands for the pure components of the mixture. Using equations (6) to (9), we get

$$B^E = \frac{1}{2.5 RT} [\sum X_i \{ 2.5 B_i RT - (P_e + P_i)(V_i - V_{ei}) \} + \Delta H^M + (P_e + P_{im})(V_m - V_{im})] - \sum X_i B_i \quad (10)$$

In equation (10) we can safely write, $(P_e + P_{im}) \simeq P_{im}$ as $P_e \ll P_{im}$ and $(V_m - V_{im}) \simeq \sum X_i V_i - \sum X_i V_{ei}$ as $(V^E - V_s^E)$ is negligible. In order to calculate B^E using equation (10) alongwith equations (3) and (4), we need $\Delta H^M - X - T$, $P_{im} - X - T$, $V_m - X - T$, $V_{im} - X - T$ and $\gamma_{sm} - X - T$ data. In case $P_{im} - X - T$ data are not readily available, the values of P_{im} can be calculated using the corresponding viscosity data by using the equation⁸,

$$P_{im} = \frac{(K^{1/2} b_p)_m RT \eta_m^{1/2} \rho_m^{1/3}}{u_m^{1/2} M_m^{7/6}} \quad (11)$$

where b_p and K are constants, u is the velocity of sound, η the viscosity, ρ the density and M the molecular weight. For most of the liquids the values of the constants b_p and K are taken as 2 and 4.28×10^9 respectively. Alternatively, b_p and K may be combined as one adjustable parameter and evaluated for pure components if P_i values are known. The mixture quantities $(K^{1/2} b_p)_m$ and M_m are then obtained by usual mixture rules. For η_m , ρ_m and u_m , the experimental values are preferred. In an extreme case, when no experimental data are available, the group contribution method may be adopted for calculating P_i using the equations⁴,

$$P_i = n \delta_i^2 \quad (12)$$

with

$$\delta_i = (\rho_i / M_i) \sum F_k \quad (13)$$

where δ_i is the solubility parameter of the component (i) and F_k the group contribution by group K of component i, and n is a constant approximately equal to 1 for non-hydrogen bonded liquids.

Results and Discussion

According to association theory, its characteristic parameter (B) is a measure of the molecular species present in a liquid system and the excess quantity B^E as defined by equation (9) for a liquid mixture is a measure of the change in molecular species as a result of nonideality in the mixing process. Accordingly, the positive value of B^E indicates an increase in the number of molecular species as a consequence of breaking of association bonds on mixing. On the other hand, the negative value of B^E indicates a decrease in the number of molecular species as a consequence of the formation of additional association bonds on mixing. It may further be noted that according to equation (10), B^E for a liquid mixture with known composition, temperature and external pressure, is a function of the mixture properties ΔH^M , P_{im} , V_m and V_{im} alongwith the corresponding pure component properties P_{ii} , V_i , V_{ei} and B_i and reflects the combined effect of the non-idealities in all these parameters. It is because of this that B^E is considered to be an appropriate indicator to assess the variations in the nature and the extent of the liquid structuration through multimer formation involving association bonds.

In order to assess the usefulness of the parameter B^E for interpreting the non-ideality in the mixing process, B^E values for some typical binary mixtures, viz. (A) benzene (1) + carbon tetrachloride (2), (B) acetone (1) + chloroform (2), (C) benzene (1) + *p*-dioxane (2), (D) acetone (1) + carbon disulphide (2), (E) benzene (1) + *p*-xylene (2), (F) dichloromethane (1) + toluene (2) and (G) dichloromethane (1) + benzene (2) were calculated using equation (10) alongwith equations (3) and (4) and are listed in Table 1. Required as input for equation (10), $\Delta H^M - X - T$ data⁵ for the binaries (A) to (G), $P_{im} - X - T$ data^{6,7} for binaries (A) to (E), $V_i - T$ data⁸ and $V_{ei} - T$ data⁸ for the binaries (A) to (G) and V_{ei} data¹ for the binary (A) were taken from the literature. As the $P_{im} - X - T$ data for the binaries (F) to (G) were not readily available, the same were obtained by equation (11) for which the needed input data were used as reported elsewhere⁷. The V_{ei} data for the binaries (B) to (G) were obtained using the equation¹⁰,

$$V_{ei} = V_i (1 - T/T_{ci})^{0.3} \quad (14)$$

where T_{ci} is the critical temperature of component i.

Since it is reasonable to expect that for the same liquid mixture, the sign and the variation in the magnitude of B^E should be consistent with the sign and variations in the magnitude of some other typical excess properties, the values of B^E were compared with the corresponding values of enthalpy of mixing (ΔH^M), excess internal pressure (P_i^E), and the related excess heat of evaporation (ΔH_v^E) (Table 1). The values of ΔH^M are readily available in literature⁵ while P_i^E and ΔH_v^E were calculated by equation (9) replacing B by P_i or H_i

as the case may be. Further, the values of ΔH_v were calculated from known values of P_i by the equation,

$$\Delta H_v = P_i V + RT \quad (15)$$

A close scrutiny of the values of B^E , ΔH^M , P_i^E and ΔH_v^E as listed in Table 1 for the binaries considered, reveals the following.

TABLE 1 - VALUES OF B^E , ΔH^M , P_i^E AND ΔH_v^E FOR THE BINARY MIXTURES

X_1	B^E	ΔH^M J mol ⁻¹	P_i^E atm	ΔH_v^E kcal
Benzene (1)+carbon tetrachloride (2) at 303 K				
0.2	0.011 6	82.0	-21.0	-0.018
0.4	0.019 9	123.0	-7.0	-0.012
0.6	0.024 9	123.0	26.0	0.051
0.8	0.005 0	82.0	34.0	0.054
1.0	0	0	0	0
Acetone (1)+chloroform (2) at 393 K				
0.2	-0.174	-1350.0	-7.0	-0.016
0.4	-0.350	-1970.0	-65.0	-0.191
0.6	-0.306	-1720.0	-74.0	-0.166
0.8	-0.166	-96.0	-2.0	-0.058
1.0	0	0	0	0
Benzene (1)+ <i>p</i> -dioxane (2) at 293 K				
0.249 7	0.193	-1.0	3.0	0.018
0.500 5	0.381	-32.0	18.0	0.049
0.750 3	0.555	-49.0	10.0	0.033
1.0	0	0	0	0
Acetone (1)+carbon disulphide (2) at 293 K				
0.2	0.088	621.5	-86.0	-0.112
0.4	0.097	731.0	-131.0	-0.177
0.6	0.088	655.0	-107.0	-0.146
0.8	0.051	463.7	-114.0	-0.174
1.0	0	0	0	0
Benzene (1)+ <i>p</i> -xylene (2) at 298 K				
0.261 7	0.201	119.0	-35.0	-0.041
0.501 5	0.350	167.0	-50.0	-0.058
0.750 1	0.526	133.0	-4.0	-0.041
1.0	0	0	0	0
Dichloromethane (1)+toluene (2) at 298 K				
0.100 6	-0.025	-97.1	-0.837	0.011
0.301 1	-0.054	-206.8	-2.781	-0.003
0.499 9	-0.063	-216.6	-4.079	-0.023
0.699 6	-0.055	-151.9	-4.063	-0.032
0.899 0	-0.008	-40.7	-1.419	-0.033
1.0	0	0	0	0
Dichloromethane (1)+benzene (2) at 298 K				
0.098 8	-0.025	-126.0	-0.163	0.000 4
0.300 4	-0.014	-54.2	-0.850	-0.006 1
0.600 0	-0.048	-82.7	-1.440	-0.022 0
0.800 4	-0.020	-55.3	-0.539	0.017 5
0.900 0	-0.010	-30.3	-0.158	0.021 4
1.0	0	0	0	0

Benzene (1)+carbon tetrachloride (2) at 303 K: In the composition range $0 < X_1 < 0.5$, ΔH^M is positive showing that the association bonds within the multimers break while P_i^E and H_v^E are negative showing that the attraction among the multimers and/or unimers decreases during the mixing process.

However, in the composition range $0.5 < X_1 < 1.0$, ΔH^M as well as P_i^E and ΔH_v^E are all positive, indicating that the intra-multimer association bonds break but at the same time the inter-species attraction increases as a result of mixing. However, since B^E is positive throughout the composition range, the energetic effects lead to breaking of the association bonds within the multimers throughout resulting in the overall decrease in structuration even though the inter-species attraction increases in the composition range $0.5 < X_1 < 1.0$.

Acetone (1)+chloroform (2) at 293 K: The values of ΔH^M , P_i^E and ΔH_v^E are all negative throughout the composition range. The negative ΔH^M values indicate that the formation of intra-multimer association bonds increases while the negative P_i^E and ΔH_v^E values show that the inter-species attraction decreases. However, since B^E values are negative throughout the composition range, energetic effects lead to the formation of the additional association bonds within the multimers as a result of mixing throughout the composition range leading to the overall increase in structuration.

*Benzene (1)+*p*-dioxane (2) at 298 K:* Throughout the composition range, ΔH^M is negative while P_i^E and ΔH_v^E are both positive. Accordingly, the intra-multimer association bonds are formed and the inter-species attraction increases. In view of the fact that B^E values are all positive throughout the composition range, energetic effects lead to the breaking of intra-multimer association bonds even though the overall structuration may not decrease as a result of mixing.

*Acetone (1)+carbon disulphide (2) at 293 K and benzene (1)+*p*-xylene (2) at 298 K:* Throughout the composition range, ΔH^M is positive while P_i^E and ΔH_v^E are both negative. Accordingly, the intra-multimer association bonds are broken and the inter-species attraction decreases. Also, since B^E values are positive, the intra-multimer association bonds break and the overall energetic effects lead to decreased structuration.

Dichloromethane (1)+benzene (2) and dichloromethane (1)+toluene (2) at 298 K: Throughout the composition range, ΔH^M and P_i^E are negative indicating that intra-multimer association bonds are formed and the inter-species attraction decreases as a result of mixing. As regards ΔH_v^E values, these are positive as well as negative in different regions showing that some unknown steric factors concerning multimeric aggregate formation are involved. However, since B^E values are all negative, the intra-multimer association bonds are formed and the energetic effects lead to the increase of overall structuration.

From the above discussion it is obvious that the knowledge of the variations in either ΔH^M , P_i^E or

ΔH_v^E alone is insufficient to assess the resultant variations in the liquid structuration due to mixing process. The knowledge of the association theory parameter B^E is also needed to explain the apparent inconsistencies in ΔH^M , P_i^E and ΔH_v^E values and for the assessment of the resultant variations in the nature and the extent of molecular structurations leading to non-idealities in liquid mixtures.

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